

Full name: _____

Generative AI tools usage survey

Please, indicate whether you have used any generative AI (GenAI) tool in the indicated project execution areas and evaluate its usefulness according to the following scale:

1. Low or none: completely incorrect responses.
2. Moderately useful: responses that required to be modified.
3. Highly useful: almost) complete and functional responses

If you have used several GenAI tools in the same area, you may also indicate this.

PROJECT EXECUTION AREA	GenAI employed (ordered by usage frequency)	USEFULNESS		
		1 low or none	2 mode- rate	3 high
Learning new technologies				
Use cases and test specifications				
Prototyping (user interface design, branding, etc.)				
Design patterns (ideas, UML diagrams generation, etc.)				
Development planning (cost estimation, risk assessment, scheduling, etc.)				
Implementation and debugging (code assistance, error resolution, etc.)				

Thank you for your contribution